

Panchayat Election In Jammu and Kashmir 2011: A Case Study In Kulgam District

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to analyze the people's participation in the 2011 panchayat elections and success of panchayati raj institutions. These elections were held after a long gap of 10 years, on the non-party basis with 33% reservations for women, only in Panch Seats. According to the new system people were directly voted, to elect Panchs and sarpanchs at Halqa level. The state election department had prepared fresh data about the number of Panchayats and Panch Constituencies in Jammu and Kashmir. The state has total 52 Lakh voters eligible for voting during Panchayat polls of 2011, around two lakh of these voters were exercised their right for the first time. Following the updation of the electoral rolls, the number of Panchayats and panch constituencies have gone up to 4131 and 29710 respectively across Jammu and Kashmir. The study is an empirical study based on primary date. The study was conducted in one randomly selected panchayat of kulgam block of District Kulgam. The study unfolds awareness of the people about powers and functions of panchayat system, affiliation of people with a political party, the participation of people in panchayat elections, issues on which panchayat elections fought, rate of success of panchayats, criteria of getting votes in villages and the responsibility of village development.

Key Words: Panchayat Election, Jammu and Kashmir, people, village, panchayat system, Kulgam, Participation.

Introduction:

Elections are an important aspect of the democratic process. When democratic institutions are considered desirable at the village level to stimulate development, elections based on universal adult suffrage become mandatory. An election not only provides opportunities for people to choose their representatives but was a process of political education. It is also a process of mobilization of people for involving them in developmental activity. It helps the identification of people with the institutions and is the best outlet for increasing

competitiveness in rural India. The election to Panchayats is the most important feature which distinguishes the statutory Panchayats from traditional Panchayats¹.

The process for the conduct of Panchayat polls in Jammu & Kashmir finally took immediately after the budget session of the state legislature commenced from 28 February 2011. The elections were held on a non-party basis in three phases and the whole process was completed by November 2011. The decision was taken by the state cabinet, which met under the chairmanship of then Chief Minister Omer Abdullah. The cabinet also cleared the proposal for lowering the minimum age bar for becoming the member of Halqa Panchayat from 25 to 21. It also approved to complete the main election process of electing panch and sarpanch by May 2011. The schedules for these polls were worked out in consultation with the state's chief electoral officer. Around 29400 panchs and sarpanchs were elected in the first phase, which includes nearly 9000 women as 33% of the seats were reserved for the fair sex². In Jammu and Kashmir the Panchayat polls were held in 2011 after a gap of ten years from 13 April 2001 as the state's chief electoral officer (CEO) 15 March 2011 issued the notification announced the schedule for 16 phase's (but actually held in 17 phases) rural local body elections³.

Kulgam district has five Blocks, 159 panchayats and 1060 panch constituencies and polling stations respectively. In 2011 Kulgam district has 193074 Lakh voters. The state government deployed 1974 security personnel for Kulgam District during these elections. In Kulgam district these elections were held in five phases. In the first phase, the polling was held in CD block Qaimoh which is divided into two revenues of district Kulgam and Anantnag. Anantnag consists of 13 Halqas while as Kulgam comprises of 23 Halqas. In this block 77.34% of poll percentage was recorded⁴. In the second phase, polling was held in CD block Pahloo in 17 sarpanch and 123 panch constituencies. The polling percentage recorded as 81.48%⁵. In the third phase, polling was held in CD block Kulgam in 33 sarpanch and 216 panch constituencies. As 79 % of polling was recorded in block kulgam⁶. In the fourth phase, the polling was held in CD block Devsar in 33 sarpanch and 239 panch constituencies. Eighty per cent of polling was recorded in block Devsar of Kulgam district⁷. In the fifth phase polling was held in CD block D H Pora in 53 sarpanchs and 322 panch constituencies, 83.18 % of polling was recorded in D H Pora block⁸. The overall percentage remained 80.20 % in all five blocks of the Kulgam district.

Table 1: DETAILED STATEMENT OF ELECTED SARPANCHS/PANCHS OF KULGAM DISTRICT

Name of block	No. of panchayat halqas/ sarpanch const.	Candidates Elected			No of sarpanch vacancies	No. of panchayat panch const.	Candidates Elected			No of panch vacancies
		Male	Female	Total			Male	Female	Total	
Devsar	33	33	0	33	0	239	162	76	238	1
D.H.Pora	53	53	0	53	0	322	216	106	322	0
Kulgam	33	33	0	33	0	216	148	65	213	3
Pahloo	17	17	0	17	0	123	84	39	123	0
Qaimoh	23	22	0	22	1	160	106	38	144	16
Total	159	158	0	158	1	1060	716	324	1040	20

Source: Election Authority of Jammu and Kashmir

Perception of people of District Kulgam

Table 2: Gender wise distribution of respondents

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Male	67	67%
Female	33	33%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

The data in table 2 shows the gender wise distribution of the respondents selected in the study. The maximum number of respondents was male (67 per cent) and a minimum number of respondents are female (33 per cent).

Table 3: Age wise distribution of respondents

Age	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Up to 25 years	21	21%
26 to 35 years	24	24%

36 to 45 years	25	25%
46 to 55 years	15	15%
56 and above years	15	15%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

In the above table, the data represents that a maximum number of respondents are below the age of 45 years as India has a large number of the youth population. As 21 per cent are in the age group up to 25 years while 24 per cent are in the age group of 26 to 45 years. A quarter of respondents are in the age group of 36 to 45 years and the same numbers of respondents are in the age group of 46 to 55 years and 56 to above years of age.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents on the basis of the Size of Family

Size of Family	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Nuclear	73	73%
Joint Family	27	27%
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 highlights the size of the family, 73% of the respondents have a nuclear family and 27% have a joint family. The data presents that the majority of respondents had a nuclear family.

Table 5: Affiliation of respondents with a political party

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	13	13%
No	87	87%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 highlights the affiliation of respondents with political parties. The maximum numbers of respondents have not affiliated with the political parties. The cause behind this was the effect of insurgency which afraid the people of the valley to affiliate with any political group.

Table 6: Awareness of the respondents regarding the powers and function of the Panchayat System

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	78	78%
No	22	22%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 6 depicts the awareness of respondents regarding the powers and functions of the Panchayat system of Jammu and Kashmir. Seventy-eight per cent of the respondents are responded that they are aware of the powers and functions of Panchayat system. It indicates that there is the majority of the respondents which are aware of the powers and functions of Panchayat system.

Table 7: Distribution of respondents on the basis of casting vote in Panchayati election

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	77	77%
No	23	23%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

The data in Table 7 indicates the percentage of respondent's casting vote in Panchayat elections of 2011. The maximum number of respondents with 77% cast votes in the election. It indicates that people want the panchayat representatives of their choice in villages, so that they can solve their local problems well.

Table 8: Distribution of respondents on the basis of issues on which Panchayat elections are fought

Issues	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Village development and improvement	61	61%
Poverty eradication	12	12%
Educational development	04	05%
Social work	14	14%
Women and child welfare	09	09%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 8 represents the issues on which Panchayat elections are conducted. The maximum numbers of respondents (61%) are of the opinion that the elections are conducted for the development and improvement of villages. It urges the people to come out and participate actively in the Panchayat elections of 2011. As they want the development of their villages.

Table 9: Distribution of respondents on the basic criteria of getting votes to members

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Personal image	65	65%
Party support	17	17%
Popularity	07	07%

Caste basis	02	02%
Issue-based	09	09%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 9 highlights the criteria of getting votes. The data shows that 65% of the respondents opined that the criterion of getting votes to members is his/her personal image. It indicates that the personal image of Candidate impacts the choice of voters in villages. The reason was also that elections are conducted on non-party basis.

Table 10: Distribution of respondents on the basis of woman participation in Panchayati elections

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	74	74%
No	26	26%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

The data in Table 10 highlights the participation of women in Panchayati elections. Seventy-four per cent of the respondents responded that the women participated in the Panchayati elections of 2011. It indicates that women also want development of villages which clicked them to vote in 2011 panchayat elections.

Table 11: Distribution of respondents on the basis of the rate of the success of panchayat in Jammu and Kashmir

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Very good	31	31%
Good	24	24%
Satisfactory	34	34%
Unsatisfactory	11	11%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 11 indicates the success rate of Panchayats in Jammu and Kashmir. Thirty-four of the respondents are responded that the rate of success of Panchayats in Jammu and Kashmir is satisfactory, 31% consider it very good, 24% responded as good. It shows the majority of the

respondents are replied that the success rate of Panchayat in Jammu and Kashmir is satisfactory.

Table 12: Distribution of respondents on the fact that the development of the village is a collection responsibility of all Panchayat representatives

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	91	91%
No	09	09%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 12 shows that the majority of respondents that is 91% endorse the fact that the development of the village is a collective responsibility of all panchayat representatives. It indicates that for village development there should be cooperation among villagers and panchayat representatives.

Table 13: Classification of respondents on the basis of change seen in the village after the Panchayat Raj system

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	43	43%
No	57	57%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 13 represents the majority of respondents that is 57% do not see the change in villages due to the Panchayat Raj system, while 43% says that there are some changes due to it.

Table 14: Distribution of respondents on the basis of opinions with regard to village development

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Economic development	22	22%
Development of physical infrastructure	56	56%
Quality education	10	10%
Health facilities	12	12%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 14 shows that the majority of respondents that is 50% are of the view that the development takes place in terms of physical structure, 22% responded as economic development, 12% opined as health facilities, 10% responded as quality education.

Table 15: Classification of Respondents on the basis of the cause of Panchs/Sarpanchs Resignation

Options	Number of Respondents	Percentage
Lack of security arrangements	70	70%
The killing of panchs/sarpanchs	27	27%
Lack of powers	03	03%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 15 highlights the cause behind the resignation of elected panchs/sarpanchs, 70% of the respondents responded that the panchs/sarpanchs give resignation because of lack of security arrangements, 27% opined because of killings and 3% argued due to lack of powers. It represents the majority of respondents argued that the panchs/sarpanchs give resignation because of lack of security arrangements by the state government.

Democracy can be truly empowering at the grass root level only when it is fully active according to the needs and aspirations of peoples. For sustainable rural development, good governance at the grass root level is mandatory. Governance is not only to govern but to be governed in accordance with the plans set up by the masses at the grass root level⁹. The need of the hour is now to empower these panchayats so that they are in a position to generate revenue and utilize it for the development of villages. For this purpose the people of the state in general and Valley particular castes their vote in 2011 panchayat elections.

Conclusion:

The local people can solve the local problems well, as they are well familiar with the local surroundings. This initiates the people to come out and select their choice of panchayat representatives in 2011. The people expect that these representatives will work for the development of villages. They thought that the development of villages is the collective responsibility of villagers and all panchayat representatives. A large number of women also participates in these elections and supports their male members to select the chosen candidates. The infrastructural development was seen in villages after panchayat representatives elected but due to militant threats they resigned which now hurdles in the developmental works.

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